

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING VOCABULARY

Students: Mamazokirova.Muhlisa

Abduvahobova.Go‘zaloy

mukhlisa473@gmail.com

gozal4218@gmail.com

Scientific supervisor: Yusupova.L

Abstract: This bachelor thesis concerns the topic of learning new vocabulary of English as a foreign language. The main question of the research is whether learners are interested in using an online vocabulary learning application.

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The evolution of methods of teaching foreign language begun before we were able to put our words on paper. Arguably the process is as old as languages themselves since people have been meeting other people not speaking the same language and yet have had to find a common language to communicate. Over the times people realised that knowing another language or more languages can open doors to new worlds and started to focus on learning a foreign language.

We could not talk about vocabulary teaching nowadays without mentioning Lewis (1993), whose controversial, thought-provoking ideas have been shaking the ELT world since its publication. I do not intend to offer a complete review of his work, but rather mention some of his contributions that in our opinion can be readily used in the classroom. Lewis' most important contribution was to highlight the importance of vocabulary as being basic to communication. We do agree that if learners do not recognise the meaning of keywords they will be unable to participate in the conversation, even if they know the morphology and syntax. On the other hand, we believe that grammar is equally important in teaching, and therefore in our opinion, it is not the case to substitute grammar teaching with vocabulary teaching, but that both

should be present in teaching a foreign language. Lewis himself insists that his lexical approach is not simply a shift of emphasis from grammar to vocabulary teaching, as 'language consists not of traditional grammar and vocabulary, but often of multi-word prefabricated chunks' (Lewis, 1997). Chunks include collocations, fixed and semifixed expressions and idioms, and according to him, occupy a crucial role in facilitating language production, being the key to fluency.

The principles of the memory card There are certain rules for creating memory cards developed by Tony Buchan, which are described in detail in his book "How to Mind Map", namely: 1. The main idea, problem or word is located in the center. Highlighting the keyword of the associative chain, Busan gives almost the main meaning 2. To depict a central idea, you can use drawings, pictures. 3. Each main branch has its own color. 4. Only colored pencils, markers, etc. are used to create maps. 5. The main branches are connected with the central idea, and the branches of the second, third, etc. orders are connected to the main branches. 6. The branches should be curved, not straight (like branches of a tree). 7. Above each line - a branch is written only one keyword. The result of the work is an individual product of one person or one group. Expresses individual capabilities, creates a space for the manifestation of creative abilities. Benefits of Mental Cards • convenient to use • show the connections between phenomena, the logic of thinking • contribute to better storage of information • collect a large amount of data together • develop creativity, thinking This technique is good to use in group work at the stage of consolidating the lexical material covered on a specific topic.

Rhymes, poems, songs The study of lexical units takes place in a playful way, which contributes to the comfortable state of students in the lesson. Children usually have erratic attention. Therefore, it is imperative in terms of the lesson to provide for types of work that relieve stress, switch the attention of children, cause a positive emotional mood. Learning rhymes, poems meets the age and psychological characteristics of children. They are easy to memorize, possess such characteristics as rhythm, sound repeatability. Learning poetry gives children pleasure. And what is experienced emotionally positively remains in the memory for a long time, leaving a mark on the child's mind. Thanks to rhyme, lexico-grammatical structures are easily activated in oral speech. The crucial point here is the use of an authentic speech pattern, and here songs and poems have many advantages over prose material. They are easy to enter, easy to remember, you can sing in chorus, which removes the psychological press from insecure students. In genuine song material, whole phrases and individual

lexical units are often found that are characteristic of colloquial speech. Crosswords are a great way for students to activate vocabulary. This strategy can be used in the first lesson of a new topic. Students will remember the words they will use in the next lesson. A crossword puzzle is a great way to repeat the previously learned words of the topic they have learned. They will repeat their spelling, remember the meanings. For weak students, you can add a thematic list of words to the crossword puzzle so that they can choose the right ones. Of course, the list of strategies for expanding the vocabulary of students can be continued further, and each teacher will choose those methods that are closer to him. The main thing to remember, work on vocabulary should be constant and systematic.

As English has turned into a universal language, its presence and value in the world has expanded enormously in the past decades. And no one can deny the importance of vocabulary—not only for reading achievement but also for general social and economic success. But if language teachers teach as they taught earlier, then the required goals of learning English Language may not be achieved in the present global scenario. In the past, no productive, creative and constructive activity was given to the learners to develop the vocabulary skills. With the changing needs of the hour (time), it becomes necessary to use various techniques and methods of teaching vocabulary. A teacher must make use of such techniques while teaching vocabulary. We are living in the 21st century and it is the age of technological advancement. Thus the recent trend in teaching vocabulary of using of modern technological tools is also very useful.

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